

A Covariant Lorentz Transformation Analysis of Einstein's Train and the Resolution of Relative Simultaneity

Andrew Wutke¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9983-7585>

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Abstract

Relative simultaneity (RS) is commonly presented as an unavoidable prediction of the special theory of relativity (STR), yet its physical significance versus synchronisation conventions remains debated. We analyse RS using a fully covariant Lorentz transformation (FCLT) expressed in homogeneous coordinates of the moving frame. Using the Lorentz transformation (LT) matrix representation, we show that the FCLT provides consistent equations of motion for light and arbitrary rectilinear motion, including point-event locations, while eliminating the mixed-coordinate artifacts that generate RS in standard treatments. Applied to Einstein's train, the FCLT predicts that simultaneous emissions in the embankment remain simultaneous in the train and that the physically relevant point coincidence of the two signals is invariant and uniquely determined. The non-simultaneous arrival of the signals at the train midpoint then appears as a kinematic consequence of midpoint motion rather than an RS effect. An equivalent algebraic procedure based on the inverse Lorentz transformation (ILT) reproduces the same result when an explicit time variable is present. For independent cross-validation, we analyse the Tangherlini transformation (TT), a preferred-frame relativistic framework derived from general relativity. Despite differing synchronisation conventions and the absence of RS, TT yields the same point coincidence as FCLT and ILT, indicating that STR already contains the necessary structure. Examination of the mixed-coordinate representation reveals a mechanism in which invariant temporal ordering encoded in the LT coexists with Einstein's synchronisation offsets, exposing a deeper unity between covariant and standard formulations. Within this representation, a theoretical preferred rest frame appears to emerge naturally from the symmetry condition on the point coincidence of counter-propagating signals

Keywords: Special Relativity · General Relativity · coordinate homogeneity · Lorentz invariance · Lorentz covariance · relative simultaneity · equations of motion · temporal relations

"There is more to structure in special relativity than meets the eye."

Jose G. Vargas [1]

¹ Email: Andrew.wutke@yahoo.com.au

1. Introduction

One of the most influential illustrations highlighting the unusual features of special theory of relativity (STR) is the train-embankment problem. This thought experiment is known to justify the counterintuitive concept of relative simultaneity. The train scenario was first mentioned in the widely circulated English translation of Einstein's 1905 publication [2] (p. 39), where it was invoked to judge the simultaneity of events.

Chapter IX of Einstein's popular book provides a complete presentation of the train embankment problem [3], where he presents the core implications of special relativity to a general audience, drawing attention to the controversial effects of relative simultaneity (RS) on the observer. To clarify his arguments, Einstein included a diagram of this scenario.

Figure 1 Einstein's Train-Embarkment Thought Experiment. (based on [3])

The diagram shows “a very long train travelling along the rails with the constant velocity and in the direction indicated in” Figure 1 “People travelling in this train will with advantage use the train as a rigid reference-body (co-ordinate system); they regard all events in reference to the train.” Einstein introduces “two strokes of lightning” events at points A and B, “which are simultaneous with reference to the railway embankment.” He concludes that an observer on the train “will see the beam of light emitted from B earlier than he will see that emitted from A.” Subsequently he infers that: “Events which are simultaneous with reference to the embankment are not simultaneous with respect to the train, and vice versa (relativity of simultaneity).”

Einstein's justification is primarily intuitive, and Figure 1 omits details that would facilitate a clearer interpretation, such as the location of the coordinate system origins, which would support a precise reconstruction. To introduce a more explicit physical context, we consider a train that is initially at rest, with a length equal to that of the embankment segment and is subsequently accelerated to a high velocity so that it contracts. We also consider a limiting case in which, at $t = 0$, the contracted train length matches the embankment length—corresponding to Einstein's idealised “very long train.”

We analysed the training scenario through a mathematical framework using a linear LT matrix representation and reached conclusions that differ from the standard interpretation. We show that RS reduces to a coordinate artifact arising from Einstein's synchronisation convention, carrying no frame-independent physical consequence — a conclusion supported by both the FCLT analysis and the independent Tangherlini framework."

2. Methods

We interpret the relativistic Lorentz transformation (LT) in the standard operational sense, as articulated by Rindler [4] (p. 43). A transformation relates the coordinates (ct, x, y, z) assigned to a spacetime event (or another fixed location with no associated event) from one inertial frame to the coordinates (ct', x', y', z') assigned to the same event in another inertial frame. Unprimed coordinates refer to an arbitrarily chosen “stationary” frame, and primed coordinates refer to a frame uniformly moving with

respect to it. Instead of using the traditional algebraic representation of the direct or inverse Lorentz transformations, we employ equivalent matrix representations.

The following (LT) matrix in the standard configuration was used in the following considerations:

$$\Lambda_v = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v & -v\frac{\gamma_v}{c} & 0 & 0 \\ -v\frac{\gamma_v}{c} & \gamma_v & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

We represent 4-vectors and matrices using square brackets and denote components using round brackets with subscripts, for example, $ct = (\mathbf{X})_0$. This traditional linear-algebraic notation is adopted to avoid covariant/contravariant tensor indices, which play no role in this analysis. Additionally, subscripts attached to vector and matrix symbols (e.g., \mathbf{X}_A , \mathbf{X}_B , Λ_v) serve as labels that convey specific meanings or contexts to a single symbolic entity. For example, the transformation of the light-propagation 4-vector equation of motion (EOM) is as follows:

$$\mathbf{L}' \equiv \Lambda_v \mathbf{L}_t = \Lambda_v \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ ct \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v ct - \gamma_v vt \\ \gamma_v ct - \gamma_v vt \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v(c - v)t \\ \gamma_v(c - v)t \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

Although the Lorentz group is covariant, the intermediate expressions obtained from Equation (2) are not yet written in the homogeneous coordinates of the primed frame. Covariance requires that the transformed 4-vector be expressed entirely in terms of \mathbf{t}' and the primed spatial coordinates. Until this substitution is performed, the representation remains a mixed-coordinate form and cannot be compared directly with the covariant expression for L_t . A list of the mathematical symbols used is provided on page 22.

The term 'covariance' requires clarification, as ambiguities may arise. We follow the description of Mainzer [5]: "Covariance means form invariance, that is, the form of a physical law is unchanged (invariant) with respect to transformations of reference systems." Mainzer [6] also distinguishes covariance from invariance, such that: "Invariance, in general, means that quantities or objects do not change with respect to transformations."

Consistent with our interpretation of the LT, we maintain a strict distinction between a point-event and the 4-vector coordinates used to represent it. A point-event is a unique physical occurrence grounded in physical interactions, including photons, other particles, detectors, and measuring instruments, and its existence does not depend on any coordinate framework. Therefore, the same point-event may be assigned to an unlimited number of coordinate systems across admissible systems, including systems whose coordinate structure is not physically realised. The coordinates merely track events in space and time. A similar distinction is expressed explicitly by Einstein in [3](p.115): "To say that a point-event has the X_i coordinate x_i means that the projection of the point-event on the axis of X_i , determined by rigid rods and

in accordance with the rules of Euclidean geometry, ...". Therefore spacetime coordinates are attributes of events, not events themselves.

We define 'fully covariant Lorentz transformation' (FCLT) as the Lorentz transformation expressed entirely in the homogeneous coordinates of the target frame, so that the transformed 4-vector is written as a function of t' , rather than in a form which we call a 'mixed-coordinate' representation presented in Equation (2), which does not alter the physical content. Only then does the representation capture a consistent description of the moving object without referring to an external system. The external system reference is inherent to the intermediate 'mixed-coordinate' representation. It does not define a direct internal experience but rather mathematically bridges two distinct systems in kinematic and temporal relations.

The distinction between the coordinate location assigned by a transformation and the location at which an event is physically detectable must be kept explicit. Later sections show that this distinction becomes essential when interpreting transformed event locations and their operational meaning.

A fully covariant transformation should result in the following invariant light propagation EOM as the 4-vector $L'_{t'} = [ct', ct', 0, 0]^T$. Two additional steps must be accomplished to arrive at this form. The temporal element of the FCLT implies the equation $(L')_0 = ct'$ which defines the meaning of the temporal component containing the variable t' and can be solved for t as follows:

$$(L')_0 = ct' \Rightarrow t = \frac{ct'}{\gamma_v(c - v)}. \quad (3)$$

Substituting t from Equation (3) is the only possible way to make the resulting 4-vector covariant to the stationary L_t . After substituting t in the final 'mixed-coordinate' representation vector from Equation (2), it emerges as a covariant, and in this case, also invariant:

$$L'_{t'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ ct' \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

We obtained an invariant EOM for light, which is consistent with the postulates of relativity. This method has a significant advantage over traditional manipulations with coordinate variables in physical equations and the standard set of algebraic forms of transformation Equations (5) and (6).

$$\begin{cases} t' = \gamma_v(t - vx/c^2) \\ x' = \gamma_v(x - vt) \end{cases}, \quad (5)$$

known as Direct Lorentz Transformation (DLT), and

$$\begin{cases} t = \gamma_v(t' + vx'/c^2) \\ x = \gamma_v(vt' + x') \end{cases}, \quad (6)$$

known as the Inverse Lorentz Transformation (ILT). The matrix method is algebraically equivalent to applying the ILT directly to the variables in the expressions to be transformed. For example, to convert the component $(L)_1 = ct$ into primed coordinates, we set $x = ct$ and apply the ILT by substituting for x then for t and solving the equation for x' to obtain:

$$(L)_1 = x \Rightarrow x = ct \Rightarrow ct = \gamma_v(vt' + x') \Rightarrow \left\{ c\gamma_v \left(t' + \frac{v}{c^2} x' \right) = \gamma_v(vt' + x') \right\} \Rightarrow x' = ct'.$$

This yields the covariant form of the light-propagation 4-vector. Later sections show that applying the same procedure to point-event locations leads to results that differ from standard textbook treatments.

There is a need to clarify the choice between DLT and ILT. The term 'transformation' carries some ambiguity, particularly during its application to practical problems, as warned by Zwillinger [7], who noted that avoiding confusion requires distinguishing between transformations of the plane and substitutions that implement changes in coordinates, such that the coordinates of a point in one coordinate system become the same point expressed in a different coordinate system. The latter is the intention of the LT, as inferred by Rindler [4] (p. 43).

The substitution employed by Einstein in deriving the invariance of the spherical wave [2] (p. 46) without showing the intermediate steps is consistent with that later reconstructed in detail by French [8] (p. 81). Additionally, French [8] (p. 126) derives velocity addition formulae from the ILT perspective yet applies DLT to point-events [8] (p. 93), claiming convenience and obtaining the classic prediction of RS, which, as demonstrated later, our ILT approach fails to reproduce, apparently in conflict with Einstein's train claims. Rosser [9] (p. 156) provided another example of an ILT-based derivation of plane wave invariance in an explicitly time-dependent form. Apart from these, no other examples are available in the literature. The DLT approach dominates the textbook treatments of RS, time dilation, and length contraction, following Tolman's [10] influential book in 1917.

3. Lorentz Transformation of the Einstein Train

We model the Einstein train scenario the coordinate and event structure and 4-vector representation of EOM required for a Lorentz covariant analysis of the underlying processes.

The essential elements required to address this problem are as follows:

- Coordinate system $E (ct, x, y, z)$ representing the embankment,
- Coordinate system $T (ct', x', y', z')$ representing the train moving with velocity v along the x -axis,
- Light emission event L_A coordinates from the point $(ct, 0, 0, 0)$ at $t = 0$,
- Light emission event L_B coordinates from the point $(ct, B, 0, 0)$ at $t = 0$

With these definitions, the emission events at A and B are fixed at $t = 0$ in both frames, and the subsequent path intersection points of the light signals in E and T follow directly from the Lorentz transformation. The spatial and temporal coordinates at which the light signals emitted from A and B meet in both the E and T systems are determined in the following sections.

3.1. Covariant Transformation of Coordinates of Events from the Stationary System

Before modelling Einstein's train, it is necessary to analyse the simplest case of stationary coordinates of the point-event transformation from E to the moving T-frame. Einstein has not demonstrated an LT-based derivation, relying instead on intuitive reasoning about the clock's synchronisation with light signals prior to DLT derivation [2], p. 42. One of the earliest explicit textbook derivations using the DLT appeared in Tolman [10] (p. 52). From the derived formula, 25 in [10], rearranged and represented using our notation as

$$t_B - t_0 = \frac{v}{c} \gamma_v \frac{(x_0 - x_B)}{c},$$

we infer that, for point $x = B$ in the E system, the transformed x -coordinates in the moving frame is

$x' = \gamma_v B$. This inference is confirmed by extending Tolman's approach to the spatial component of the DLT.

$$x' = \gamma_v(x - vt),$$

which for point B it is

$$x' = -v\gamma_v t + \gamma_v B.$$

This confirms that at $t = 0$, if a train has rest length B and retains this value in its own coordinates while in motion, the mixed-coordinate expression $x' = \gamma_v B$ would appear to represent an *enlarged* embankment interval. Such an inference contradicts the reciprocity principle, which requires that a stationary object observed from a moving frame appear *contracted*, not expanded. The contradiction shows that the mixed-coordinate form cannot be used to infer consistent spatial lengths or event coordinates, because it combines the moving spatial coordinate x' with the untransformed embankment time t , producing a non-covariant and therefore misleading representation.

The difficulty arises from the *mixed-coordinate representation* used above. The expression

$$x' = -v\gamma_v t + \gamma_v B$$

is not covariant because the time coordinate has not been transformed. To restore the covariance, we solve the temporal DLT for t , substitute it into the spatial expression, and simplify. This yields the following homogeneous covariant form:

$$x' = -vt' + \frac{B}{\gamma_v},$$

which exactly satisfies reciprocity and shows that the earlier inference of an expanded embankment interval was an artifact of the mixed-coordinate form.

This demonstrates that mixed-coordinate expressions depending on their treatment can yield contradictory spatial interpretations. The implications for simultaneity arguments are examined in Section 4.3

The usual interpretation of contraction from the perspective of the E-frame dictated the initial choice of the modelled train length; the initial rest length matched the embankment length and then contracted arbitrarily depending on the velocity v .

The transformation of the two event coordinates using the FCLT is worth demonstrating.

Let us assume that the 4-vector \mathbf{X}_A represents a location of all possible point-events at $x = y = z = 0$ at all times t , designated as point A in the E-frame:

$$\mathbf{X}_A = \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

Similarly, a point-event 4-vector \mathbf{X}_B at $x = B$ designated as point B in the same frame:

$$\mathbf{X}_B = \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

Naturally, at $x = 0$ the transformed coordinates yield:

$$\mathbf{X}'_{At'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

At point $x = B$ the LT matrix transformation results in:

$$\mathbf{X}'_B \equiv \Lambda_v \mathbf{X}_B = \Lambda_v \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v ct - \gamma_v B \\ -\gamma_v vt + \gamma_v B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

This is not an explicit covariant form of \mathbf{X}_B . The two-step conversion to the covariant form requires $(\mathbf{X}'_B)_0 = ct'$ which defines the meaning of the temporal component variable t' and can be solved for t as follows:

$$(\mathbf{X}'_B)_0 = ct' \Rightarrow t = Bv/c^2 + t'/\gamma_v. \quad (11)$$

Substituting t from Equation (11) into Equation (10) yields the covariant position 4-vector of this event in T:

$$\mathbf{X}'_{Bt'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ -vt' + B/\gamma_v \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

The transformed coordinates differed from those of the standard STR predictions. As inferred from Tolman's result, they should be located at $x' = 0$ and $x' = \gamma_v B$ at different times, but instead they emerge as $x' = 0$ and $x' = B/\gamma_v$ at $t' = 0$. We note that in this case, the reciprocity principle is satisfied. A comparative analysis of FCLT and STR representations is presented in the table below.

Table 1 Comparison of event coordinates in the T-frame between the *FCLT* and *STR* representations.

FCLT Representation	Standard STR Representation
$\mathbf{X}'_{At'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{X}'_{Bt'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ -vt' + B/\gamma_v \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\mathbf{X}'_A = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v ct \\ -\gamma_v vt \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{X}'_B = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v ct - \gamma_v vB/c \\ -\gamma_v (c + vt)t + \gamma_v B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$
$x'_A(0) = 0 \quad x'_B(0) = B/\gamma_v$	$x'_A(0) = 0 \quad x'_B(0) = \gamma_v B$
$\Delta t' = 0$	$\Delta t' = -\gamma_v vB/c^2$
$\Delta x'(0) = B/\gamma_v$	$\Delta x'(0) = \gamma_v B$

The difference in the initial transformed location $x'_B(0)$ reflects the distinct analytical roles of the FCLT and the mixed-coordinate STR representation:

1. The FCLT and STR representations describe different analytical perspectives. In the FCLT, the embankment coordinate $x = 0$, at time $t = 0$ aligns in T at $t' = 0$ and $x' = 0$, and the contracted train occupies $0 \leq x' \leq B$ in its own frame, preserving the original longitudinal proportions. In contrast, the mixed-coordinate STR representation maps embankment point B to $x' = \gamma_v B$, as if viewed through the moving train's contracted coordinate scale, which does not satisfy the reciprocity principle.
2. The violation of reciprocity identified earlier—arising from the mixed-coordinate form and removed only after restoring covariance—indicates that standard simultaneity arguments depend on this structural feature rather than on a physical effect.
3. The geometric difference $\gamma_v B - B/\gamma_v$ follows directly from the mixed-coordinate form and requires additional analysis, which is further addressed with the help of the graphical context in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Covariant and mixed-coordinate representations of the event at $x=B$ under the Lorentz transformation.

Figure 2 illustrates the two-stage covariant transformation of the event at $x = B$. At the synchronisation instant $t = t' = 0$, the coordinate origins coincide and the mixed-coordinate form places the event at $x' = \gamma_v B$. This value reflects the mapping of the embankment coordinate through the contracted scale of the moving frame, not the intrinsic position of the event in T. After synchronisation, the primed axis advances relative to the embankment while the event coordinates remain fixed in both systems. The

covariant form $x'_B(0) = B/\gamma_v$ represents the intrinsic location of the same event in the moving frame and remains constant thereafter. The difference between $\gamma_v B$ and B/γ_v is therefore a coordinate-representation effect, not a physical displacement.

Traditional STR diagrams (as in Figure 1) depict the train as momentarily filling the embankment segment yet appearing longer on its own contracted scale ($x' = \gamma_v B$). However, the physical length of the train is not essential. What matters is that the midpoint M' lies between A and B at the instant the events occur. Assigning explicit dimensions to the train aids in visualising the relative motion of its endpoints with respect to light signals. The full analysis and details are presented in Section 3.2.

Based on our observations so far, the results of the analysis imply that:

1. In the mixed-coordinate representation, the LT provides a direct mapping from E to T rather than an intrinsic description of the moving system. The leading edge of the train is undefined unless its rest length is specified. It could be a train with an initial rest length of $\gamma_v B$ which may have contracted to fit perfectly into \overline{AB} line segment in E, depicted as the “Long Train.” In this case, we compared different trains rather than describing the same train. However, the length does not have an effect on the position of the transformed event.
2. In the FCLT representation, relative simultaneity is eliminated for a particular pair of point-event coordinates $x = 0$ and $x = B$ and $\Delta t' = 0$. The same is valid for any other pairs of point-events, not solely those occurring at time $t' = 0$. Within the STR standard 'mixed-coordinate' representation, the times of the transformed events differed by $\Delta t' \neq 0$.
3. In the FCLT representation, when two point-events occur at distinct locations, these points collectively continue moving together after the events, away from the origin of system T. While the coordinates of A and B always remain in relative rest within E, the same transformed points remain at relative rest at the same time t' not at different times as $t' + \Delta t'$
4. Thus, the FCLT removes the mixed-coordinate contribution to $\Delta t'$ for stationary point-events, yielding $\Delta t' = 0$. The resulting geometric displacement in x' reflects the difference between the intrinsic covariant description and the mixed-coordinate mapping $x' = \gamma_v B$. Its role becomes explicit in the dynamical analysis context in Section 3.2.
5. The FCLT uniquely yields a consistent, explicitly covariant 4-vector formulation for both point-events and equations of motion, achieved through a single, clean substitution of the time variable within the intermediate 4-vector structure. This avoids the additional algebraic steps that are typically required to interpret the standard STR mixed-coordinate form. The presented result is fully compatible with a train of rest length $\Delta x = B$, whose own length remains invariant: $\Delta x' = B$.
6. Regardless of the non-covariant appearance of the standard STR mixed-coordinate representation, it remains analytically indispensable and supports the broader interpretive framework developed in Section 3.2.
7. Finally, a point-event 4-vector is a special case of the time-dependent position 4-vector for rectilinear motion, with zero velocity for the event coinciding with the frame and nonzero velocity for the others.

3.2. Covariant Einstein's Train Interpretation

A covariant analysis of Einstein's train scenario is essential because this example has strongly shaped the widespread view that RS has a physical consequence. Using the framework established in Section 3.1,

we express the standard configuration in a form that separates intrinsic covariant structure from mixed-coordinate artefacts.

Two light signals are emitted simultaneously from points A and B on the embankment and later described in the moving train frame. Figure 3 reinterprets the standard diagram of Figure 1 using the covariant geometric context introduced in Figure 2.

To fully comprehend the context of the training scenario depicted in Figure 3, it must be recognised that observers in frames E and T do not exist in isolation; they observe the same photons, although they assign different coordinates to their positions and times.

This kinematic reality was acknowledged by Einstein, who noted that the observer is 'hastening towards the beam of light coming from B, while he is riding on ahead of the beam of light coming from A' [3] (p.51). Although this correctly describes the relative motion, the standard interpretation uses it to infer RS.

Figure 3 Contracted Einstein's Train Model

Figure 3 shows the contracted train frame T superimposed on the embankment frame E at the synchronisation instant $t = t' = 0$ ('ghosted' initial configuration). At this moment the coordinate origins coincide, and the mixed-coordinate mapping places the event at $x' = \gamma_v B$, while the covariant representation places it at $x'_B(0) = B/\gamma_v$. After synchronisation, the primed axis advances relative to the

embankment while the event coordinates remain fixed in both systems. This distinguishes the intrinsic covariant location of the event from the mixed-coordinate mapping.

The diagram also shows that the midpoint observer M' moves away from the invariant intersection point of the two light signals. This motion is not detectable within the train frame itself but determines how the incoming signals are encountered when described relative to the embankment.

The embankment x -axis is shown together with the contracted x' -axis, aligned at $t = 0$. This mapping clarifies how the train endpoints relate to the stationary emission points throughout the process. Continuous lines with arrows represent light propagation, while broken lines with arrows indicate the mixed-coordinate artefact associated with plotting one-way light speed in T against E -time. The diagram also includes equations governing the point-coincidence and transformed emission coordinates.

With this geometric context established, the train scenario can now be modelled directly using the methodology of Section 2 and the event transformations of Section 3.1

The light signal emitted from point A in the embankment frame E is represented by the 4-vector

$$\mathbf{L}_A = \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ ct \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

The oppositely directed light signal from point B is represented by

$$\mathbf{L}_B = \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ -ct + B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

Solving the two equations of motion yields the paths (worldlines) intersection point

$$\{c = ct, x = -ct + B\} \Rightarrow \left\{ t = \frac{B}{2c}, x = B/2 \right\}. \quad (15)$$

As expected, the light signals emitted simultaneously at $t = 0$ meet at the midpoint $x_M = B/2$ at time $t_M = B/2c$, in the embankment frame.

To ascertain the outcome within T, coordinate transformations must be performed. Applying the Lorentz-transformation matrix to \mathbf{L}_A gives a mixed-coordinate expression depending on the external stationary time t .

$$\mathbf{L}'_A \equiv \Lambda_v \mathbf{L}_A = \Lambda_v \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ ct \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v ct - \gamma_v vt \\ \gamma_v ct - \gamma_v vt \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v (c - v)t \\ \gamma_v (c - v)t \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

The transformed EOM must be reformulated in terms of homogeneous coordinates. To obtain the covariant form, the temporal component is set equal to ct' , solved for t , and substituted back into the mixed-coordinate 4-vector. The equation $(\mathbf{L}'_A)_0 = ct'$ defines the meaning of the temporal component. Solving this for t yields

$$(\mathbf{L}'_A)_0 = ct' \Rightarrow t = \frac{ct'}{\gamma_v(c-v)}. \quad (17)$$

Substitution of t from Equation (17) is the only way to make the resulting 4-vector covariant to \mathbf{L}_A . After substituting t to Equation (16) the covariant form of the light vector in T is

$$\mathbf{L}'_{At'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ ct' \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

which is invariant and consistent with the postulates of special relativity. The same procedure is applied to \mathbf{L}_B . The mixed-coordinate form is first obtained from the LT matrix, the temporal component is set equal to ct' , and the resulting expression for t is substituted back to restore covariance

$$\mathbf{L}'_B \equiv \Lambda_v \mathbf{L}_B = \Lambda_v \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ -ct + B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v(c+v)t - \gamma_v vB/c \\ -\gamma_v(c+v)t + \gamma_v B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

$$(\mathbf{L}'_B)_0 = ct' \Rightarrow t = \frac{\gamma_v vB + c^2 t'}{\gamma_v c(c+v)}. \quad (20)$$

This yields the covariant expression

$$\mathbf{L}'_{Bt'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ -ct' + \gamma_v B - \frac{\gamma_v Bv}{c} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ -ct' + \frac{\gamma_v B(c-v)}{c} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

Applying the inverse LT confirms that this expression reproduces the original \mathbf{L}_B

$$\mathbf{L}_B \equiv \Lambda_v^{-1} \mathbf{L}'_{Bt'} = \Lambda_v^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ -ct' + \frac{\gamma_v B(c-v)}{c} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ -ct + B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

Equating the covariant expressions for \mathbf{L}'_A and \mathbf{L}'_B gives the intersection time

$$\mathbf{L}'_{At'} = \mathbf{L}'_{Bt'} \Rightarrow ct' = -ct' + \frac{\gamma_v B(c-v)}{c} \Rightarrow t' = \frac{\gamma_v B(c-v)}{2c^2} \equiv t'_i, \quad (23)$$

where t'_i is the time of the light signal intersection. The intersection coordinate x'_i which can be referred to as the point-coincidence location, can be found from either light signal EOM.

$$\mathbf{L}'_{At'} = \mathbf{L}'_{Bt'} \Rightarrow x'_i = ct'_i \Rightarrow x'_i = \frac{\gamma_v B(c-v)}{2c}. \quad (24)$$

The intersection point does not coincide with the midpoint of the contracted train. Its location follows

solely from the kinematics of the covariant transformation, and there is therefore no reason to expect it to lie at the train's midpoint. This conclusion applies equally to the long-train configuration of Figure 2 which is fully compatible with Einstein's original scenario. The train length plays no role in determining the point-coincidence location; the intersection depends only on the emission-event coordinates in the embankment frame.

The emission coordinate satisfies $x'_0 = 2x'_i$, consistent with the T-frame geometry of the covariant construction of the invariant light signals.

$$x'_0 = \frac{\gamma_v B(c-v)}{c} \Rightarrow 2x'_i. \quad (25)$$

The effective point-coincidence location lies between the transformed emission points, not between the train's endpoints. Table 2 compares the covariant and mixed-coordinate STR representations.

Table 2 Comparison of events coordinates in T frame between the FCLT and standard STR representations

FCLT Representation	Standard STR Representation
$L'_{At'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ ct' \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, L'_{Bt'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ -ct' + \gamma_v B(c-v)/c \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$L'_A = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v(c-v)t \\ \gamma_v(c-v)t \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, L'_B = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_v(c+v)t - \gamma_v vB/c \\ -\gamma_v(c+v)t + \gamma_v B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$
$x'_A(0) = 0 \quad x'_B(0) = \gamma_v B(c-v)/c$	$x'_A(0) = 0 \quad x'_B(0) = \gamma_v B$
$\Delta t' = 0$	$\Delta t'(0) = -\gamma_v vB/c^2$
$\Delta x'(0) = \gamma_v B(c-v)/c$	$\Delta x'(0) = \gamma_v B$
$t'_i = \gamma_v B(c-v)/2c^2$	$t'_i = B/2c$
$x'_i = \gamma_v(c-v)B/2c$	$x'_i = \gamma_v(c-v)B/2c,$

These results differ from those in

1. Table 1, which describes stationary point-events, because the present analysis includes time-dependent light propagation. Nevertheless, both the FCLT and the mixed-coordinate STR representation predict the same point-coincidence location x'_i , indicating that both identify this intersection as an invariant event. This shows that the emergent time variable t' in the FCLT has a conceptual status independent of Einstein's synchronisation convention, and the RS arising from $\Delta x'(0) \neq 0$ does not affect the location of the point-coincidence.
2. The coordinate $x = B$ enters all expressions as a fixed embankment location; the point-coincidence location depends only on this \overline{AB} segment interval, not on the train's contracted length, which is understandable because light emission from this position is a point-coincidence of photon emission and the embankment.
3. An apparent ambiguity arises in the mixed-coordinate representation because the temporal component contains the synchronisation offset responsible for RS, while the spatial expression $x'(t)$ is a non-standard but valid equation of motion for light expressed in terms of the embankment time t . In determining the intersection point, the offset effectively cancels, giving the appearance of an absolute-like time. But this is not a physical inconsistency.
4. The form of the spatial component in mixed-coordinate representation is an intriguing hybrid. The cross-system one-way velocity of light of the two signals becomes anisotropic; however, the

intersection point remains invariant. The apparent variable velocities of light with respect to t are $c_+ = \gamma_v(c - v)$ and $c_- = -\gamma_v(c + v)$. Although the two signals coincide at the same location x'_i as in the FCLT representation, they do so at different E-time coordinates. However, when the same pair of signals is represented in the FCLT coordinates (t', x') of T, the speed of light remains invariant, and point-coincidence occurs at the same x'_i .

5. Unexpected yet algebraically inevitable, the same mixed-coordinate light propagation equations reappear when the LT matrix is replaced by the Tangherlini [11] transformation² (TT) matrix, and applied to the light-signal four -vectors L_A from Equation (13) and L_B from Equation (14) yielding the same mixed-coordinate form. This reflects the structural commonality between LT and TT in mixed-coordinate representation. The equivalence of the intermediate form equations explains why the time coordinate t' in the FCLT representation remains compatible with the invariant temporal ordering of the time coordinates, which is applicable to Tangherlini's time properties.
6. We conclude that relativistic kinematics in the STR fixes point-coincidence independently of the synchronisation conventions. The signals do not simultaneously reach the midpoint of the train because the train moves relative to the future location of the invariant intersection point.
7. Point-coincidence is the intersection of worldlines, and it is invariant under all admissible coordinate transformations.
8. The event at $x = B$ assumes different transformed coordinates depending on whether it is treated as a point-event (Figure 2) or as an emission event (Figure 3). This may seem counterintuitive because the local physics at $x = B$ is not changed neither by the train motion nor its rest length. The difference arises solely from the synchronisation convention embedded in the LT; its role is to enforce the light-speed postulate, not to preserve geometric intuition. In the absence of light (Figure 2), the transformed point-event coordinates reflect only the synchronisation convention.
9. For light, the Lorentz transformation must preserve the fixed point coincidence and enforce isotropic propagation in the moving frame. These two physical constraints uniquely determine the emission coordinates, leaving no freedom to place the emission point at its original location in the stationary frame. By contrast, a point-event in the embankment frame is simply the physical coincidence of light and matter, and no additional constraint exists that would justify shifting its location
10. Importantly, no part of the contracted train ever coincided with $x = B$ during the experiment; no local sensor in the train could detect emission or acquire a "burn mark" from the lightning strike. It is a coordinate artifact whose role is to preserve the invariance of the true point-coincidence, which is the only element of physical significance.

As noted previously, the train analysed above is not the same as the train depicted in Figure 1, and the train length has no bearing (on the) invariant location of the light signals point-coincidence. For clarity, Einstein's $x_i = ct_i = \frac{x_0}{\gamma_v} = \frac{x_0}{2c}$ "very long train" is presented in

Figure 4. Our conclusions are ultimately applicable to this configuration.

For the same velocity and contraction factor, the train's length is greater than that of the former train because it includes a larger number of wagons. It is also the shortest train of this type, for which the emission events at points A and B coincide with both the train and the embankment.

² Tangherlini's original theory was presented in the 1958 Stanford PhD dissertation [11]. A brief overview is given in Section 3.3

Figure 4 No effect of the train length on the point-coincidence location. In this case, both emission events physically coincide on the train and embankment, where they could be detected.

It can be concluded that symmetric light signals reach the midpoint between their emission locations $(0, x'_0)$ simultaneously in the local coordinates instead of point M' . This observation diverges from Einstein's 1921 assertion that events do not arrive at the midpoint simultaneously because of the relative simultaneity. This issue requires a broader synthesis, as discussed in Section 4.2.

3.3. Tangherlini Framework Supporting the Resolution of Relative Simultaneity.

The disappearance of RS in the FCLT representation and inverse LT substitution method warrants independent theoretical cross-validation. Direct experimental verification of the train–embankment scenario is not feasible with the required precision, and Einstein's midpoint observer construction remains purely conceptual.

A suitable theoretical comparison is provided by the Tangherlini relativistic framework [11], which postulates a preferred rest frame and employs the absolute Tangherlini transformation (TT). TT was originally obtained as a special-case solution of Einstein field equations in flat space [11], but it can also be derived independently from first principles, analogous to Einstein's postulates. Selleri's formulation [12] is an example. It assumes isotropy of the average roundtrip light speed while allowing anisotropy of the one-way velocity relative to inertial systems moving with an absolute velocity relative to the absolute

reference frame (ARF). Consequently, it does not follow Einstein's synchronisation convention.

Both the Tangherlini and Einstein–Lorentz frameworks are sub-theories of general relativity (GR) and must therefore agree on all coordinate-independent physical predictions. In particular, they must yield identical point-coincidence locations, which—as Einstein emphasised—they "amount to a determination of space-time coincidences." They constitute only empirically accessible space-time data. In the Tangherlini framework, the moving clock rate depends on the absolute velocity, and the time coordinate contains no spatial offset term; thus, the TT has no analogue of the RS effect.

This motivates the following hypothesis, which is currently restricted to the present scenario:

Hypothesis 1.

The point-coincidence of events is independent of the coordinate choice. Consequently, RS has no physical effect because it does not exist in the TT framework.

Although this follows directly from the general covariance, it is instructive to explicitly examine the mechanism. The hypothesis is sufficiently supported if the two signals meet at the same coordinate location on the shared x' -axis in both frameworks, which is common to the Tangherlini and Einstein frameworks in the standard configuration. The TT matrix is defined as

$$\Omega_v^\infty = \begin{bmatrix} 1/\gamma_v & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -v\frac{\gamma_v}{c} & \gamma_v & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

$$\text{where } \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v/c^2}.$$

The factor γ_v in this case, the factor γ_v refers to the absolute velocity in the ARF, which is the only frame in which the one-way speed of light is isotropic, according to Tangherlini. This is in contrast to the Lorentz transformation, which assumes that each inertial system is at rest in its own coordinates. For the abstract comparisons that follow, we simply take the velocity parameter v in Lorentz coordinates—when spatially aligned with the Tangherlini coordinates—to be numerically equal to the absolute velocity v used in the Tangherlini framework. This identification is purely notational: within the Lorentz description, it makes no physical difference whether the rest frame is labelled 'absolute,' since each inertial frame is treated as being at rest in its own coordinates and light velocity is always isotropic.

We perform the first stage of the transformation by multiplying the TT matrix by the light 4-vectors L_A and L_B .

$$L'_{AT} \equiv \Omega_v^\infty L_A = \Omega_v^\infty \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ ct \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} ct/\gamma_v \\ \gamma_v(c - v)t \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

Then for L'_{BT} :

$$\mathbf{L}'_{BT} \equiv \Omega_v^\infty \mathbf{L}_B = \Omega_v^\infty \begin{bmatrix} ct \\ -ct + B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} ct/\gamma_v \\ -\gamma_v(c + v)t + \gamma_v B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (28)$$

Although these expressions can be converted to a fully covariant form, this is unnecessary here because we need the mixed-coordinate form to compare with that obtained in the first step of the LT matrix multiplication. As discussed in Section 3.2 paragraph 3 and 5, the x' -components in these mixed-coordinate expressions are valid equations of motion for the light signals in the train frame when expressed as functions of embankment time t . Remarkably, the spatial x' expressions in Equations (27) and (28) are identical to the corresponding Lorentz-based equations (16) and (19). Setting the two x' -components equal yields the intersection time t'_{iT} .

$$(\mathbf{L}'_{AT})_1 = (\mathbf{L}'_{BT})_1 \Rightarrow \gamma_v(c - v)t = -\gamma_v(c + v)t + \gamma_v B \Rightarrow t = B/2c \equiv t_{iT}. \quad (29)$$

and substituting into either equation of motion yields the intersection position x'_{iT} .

$$x'_{iT} = \gamma_v(c - v)t_{iT} \Rightarrow x'_{iT} = \frac{\gamma_v(c - v)B}{2}. \quad (30)$$

This confirms that the point coincidence is invariant under both transformations, thereby validating Hypothesis 1, which is exactly the same as that obtained from the FCLT in the STR framework, as shown in Equation (24). The agreement between the two frameworks is noteworthy, given that they are often regarded as conceptually incompatible in the literature without foundational proof.

The significance lies not only in the covariance but also in the fact that the Tangherlini structure emerges naturally from the internal algebraic structure of the Lorentz transformation. This is noteworthy because it is explicit and does not require additional assumptions pertaining to Tangherlini framework. Therefore, the consistency of the two theories is enforced by general covariance, confirming Hypothesis 1.

- the intersection point of the two light signals is independent of coordinate choice,
- No displacement of the point-coincidence occurs under the Lorentz transformation relative to the TT.
- RS does not exist in the Tangherlini framework; therefore, it does not correspond to any physical effect.
- computational demonstrations of RS in standard LT scenarios arise from coordinate conventions.

3.4. About the Reality of the Fully Covariant Trajectories

In Section Covariant Einstein's Train Interpretation we have exposed an unexpected geometric displacement between a point event located at $x = B$ and co-aligned with $x' = \gamma_v B$, such that the counter-propagating light signal between B and A which is displaced to $x' = B/\gamma_v$. This is an accurate mathematical result conveniently explained by the necessity to adhere to time coordinates convention to keep the speed of light constant. The argument is not only convenient but a rational one. We have seen the fully invariant transformation yielding the same point coincidence location of the meet point of the two signals which is the same as in the mixed coordinate EOM shown in Figure 4 as well as that obtained from fully covariant TT which is presented below without an easy detailed derivation:

In Section 3.2 we exposed an unexpected geometric displacement between a point event located at

$x = B$ and its co-aligned position $x' = \gamma_v B$. Under Lorentz simultaneity, the counter-propagating light signal from B to A is displaced to $x' = B/\gamma_v$. This is an exact mathematical result arising from adherence to the time-coordinate convention that preserves the invariance of the speed of light. The argument is not only convenient but rational.

We have shown that the FCTL yields the same point-coincidence location for the meet point of the two signals as the mixed-coordinate equations of motion in Figure 4, and likewise as the fully covariant TT expressions (given here without detailed derivation):

$$L'_{At't'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ -\gamma_v^2(c - v)t' \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, L'_{Bt't'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ -\gamma_v^2(c + v)t' + \gamma_v B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (31)$$

This is sufficient evidence that coordinate choice does not affect the location of the point coincidence.

However, a problem remains in the physical interpretation: the fully covariant EOMs do not cover the full spatial range between $x' = \frac{B}{\gamma_v}$ and $x' = \gamma_v B$, as if the signal had never occupied that region or had been emitted before the experiment. This is counterintuitive; a valid physical trajectory must cover this range. The solution is to return to the mixed-coordinate representations in Table 2 and substitute $t = \gamma_v t'$, where t and t' are proper times of the system clocks at $x = x' = 0$. The resulting realistic EOMs are

$$L'_{At'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ -\gamma_v^2(c - v)t' \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, L'_{Bt'} = \begin{bmatrix} ct' \\ -\gamma_v^2(c + v)t' + \gamma_v B \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (32)$$

The result is an exact copy of the TT expressions.

This is an important finding. From now on, STR does not require historical Tangherlini support; the Lorentz framework is self-contained and permits non-isotropic light velocities under this interpretation. There is no need to prove equivalence of the two frameworks. STR is consistent with itself.

The remaining issue is the existence of a preferred inertial frame. No such frame exists in the FCTL domain, but in the domain exposed here it follows immediately by demanding that the two signals point-coincidence location is at the midpoint between $x' = 0$ and $x' = \gamma_v B$:

:

$$x'_i = \frac{\gamma_v B(c - v)}{2c} = \frac{\gamma_v B}{2} \wedge |v| < c \Rightarrow v = 0. \quad (33)$$

Therefore, only one such inertial frame exists, which we call the preferred frame.

4. Discussion

4.1. Einstein's Train Modelling Approach

The original formulation of the train–embankment scenario in [3] (p. 51) is conceptually clear but lacks the operational details required for rigorous modelling. At a minimum, the coordinate systems and location of their shared origin must be specified at synchronisation. As shown in Figure 1, the train overlapped the embankment segment, but its physical length was not defined. Einstein referred to “a very

long train,” but the portion overlapping the embankment between A and B is not uniquely defined. This ambiguity is not an error in Einstein’s reasoning but hinders the unique mathematical reconstruction of the scenario in which it occurs. For modelling purposes, we adopt a more explicit configuration: a train of rest length $B - A$, pre-accelerated to velocity v , with its rear end aligned with point A at $t = 0$. We also found that the actual length of the train does not influence the invariant point-coincidence location.

We then apply the FCLT in matrix form, enabling the direct transformation of any equation of motion or point-event 4-vector. A difficulty arises when transforming point-event 4-vectors; the transformed coordinates differ from standard predictions, implying that simultaneous events in E remain occur simultaneously in T . A further complication appears when transforming simultaneous light-pulse emissions: the transformed emission event does not lie at the front of the contracted train, but at a different coordinate location. The analysis that resolves these issues is summarised in the following subsections.

4.2. Simultaneity of Equations of Motion and Events

Two issues require careful examination:

1. The apparent absence of RS, and
2. unexpected, transformed position displacement of the emission event.

The FCLT is essential for representing the equations of motion for light emitted from the origin and for any rectilinear motion passing through shared origins at $t = 0$. There was no restriction on the transformation of simultaneous events at $x = 0$ and $x = B$ at $t = 0$. The central physical effect at the midpoint of train M' is not related to the RS appearing in the mixed-coordinate form but to the location of the point-coincidence where the two light signals meet. As Einstein emphasised in the general-relativity section of [13] (p. 117), "space-time verifications invariably amount to a determination of space-time coincidences." In our model, the meeting point of the two signals is

$$x'_i = \frac{\gamma_v B(c - v)}{2c}.$$

This value is obtained independently from both the FCLT and the mixed-coordinate representation. Figure 3 shows that the FCLT yields isotropic light propagation in T , while the mixed-coordinate representation yields variable one-way velocities, yet both predict the same point-coincidence.

This ambiguity arises because the point-event at $x = B$ transforms to $x' = B/\gamma_v$ at $t' = 0$, which does not correspond to any physical event on the contracted train. Similarly, an apparent transformed emission event appears at $x' = \gamma_v B(c - v)/c$, lying within the contracted train rather than at its front as suggested by intuition. These transformed positions are best interpreted as virtual coordinates introduced by the synchronisation convention embedded in the LT. Their role is to enforce the invariance of the light speed, not to preserve the geometric intuition. The apparent displacement is the algebraic cost of eliminating RS from the description. It is worth noting that the location of the point-coincidence argument can be established directly within system E by elementary kinematic reasoning, without invoking any RS arguments. Consider a long train of length B like in Figure 4 while in motion, with midpoint M moving at speed v . In the embankment frame the midpoint follows the ordinary equation of motion $x_M(t) = M + vt$, while the counter-propagating light signals satisfy $x = ct$ and $x = -ct + B$. Solving these gives the coincidence time $t_i = B/(2c)$. At this moment the midpoint has advanced to $x_M(t_i) = M + vB/(2c)$, which is *not* the coincidence location. Consequently, the two light signals must pass the train’s midpoint at different times as a simple kinematic necessity. This behaviour follows entirely from the relative motion of

the midpoint and the light fronts and does not require any appeal to an RS effect. The lack of coincidence between M' and the light-signal intersection in the T-frame cannot be any different.

4.3. Resolution of Relative Simultaneity

FCLT appears to be largely absent from standard treatments. In this representation, RS does not arise; it is revealed as a mathematical artifact of the mixed-coordinate form. Of the two transformed light-signal 4-vector representations, only the FCLT consistently describes concurrent motions without reference to an external frame. The same result is obtained by an equivalent algebraic procedure based on the ILT when explicit time variables are present. Both approaches eliminate the RS, contrary to prevailing interpretations.

Historically, the ILT has been used to demonstrate standard relativistic effects, but only a few sources, namely French [8] and Rosser [9], have applied it in an explicit and technically complete manner. Even in these cases, the method is not extended to the transformation of event coordinates; instead, point-events are analysed by substituting their coordinates into the direct Lorentz transformation, yielding a mixed-coordinate representation and supporting the traditional RS interpretation. As shown on page 6, the covariant equation of motion $x' = B/\gamma_v$ can also be derived from Tolman's approach to restore the principle of reciprocity, which is violated when interpreting the mixed-coordinate transformed form. Therefore, the interpretation of RS in this form is not physical, as the resulting transformed event location is at $x' = B\gamma_v$.

4.4. Validation by Tangherlini Theory

The disappearance of the RS is a controversial claim that requires independent validation. We used the independently developed Tangherlini theory [11], which we implemented using the Tangherlini Transformation (TT). Both the Tangherlini and Einstein–Lorentz frameworks are special cases of general relativity and must therefore agree on all coordinate-independent physical predictions. In particular, they must yield identical point-coincidence locations.

In Section 3.3 that the point-coincidence predictions of the two light signals were identical in both theories. Furthermore, the mixed-coordinate equations of motion for the signals in x' components of the position 4-vectors are identical. As expected, in the FCLT representation, the two theories diverge significantly. The underlying structure of the Tangherlini framework is inherently encoded in the structure of the Lorentz transformation. This explicitly and naturally emerges from the mixed-coordinate representation, which is remarkable and warrants a general rigorous mathematical exposition that is not limited to the train scenario. Furthermore, in Section 3.4 we demonstrated that the Tangherlini equations of motion of light emerge naturally from the mixed-coordinate representation when we substitute $t = \gamma_v t'$, where t and t' are the proper times of the system clocks at $x = x' = 0$. This shows that the Tangherlini framework is not required as external support for STR; its structure is already contained within the Lorentz framework when interpreted correctly. The mixed-coordinate substitution also leads to the inevitable conclusion that a theoretical preferred inertial frame exists because only one frame yields a symmetric point-coincidence location for the two counter-propagating light signals relative to their emission points.

The disappearance of relativity of simultaneity is undoubtedly controversial. Although the result was derived directly from the structural properties of the Lorentz transformation (LT), one might still suspect that the mixed-coordinate representation introduces artifacts or relies on certain hidden assumptions. Therefore, an independent verification is required. Tangherlini's framework [11] provides these tests. The Tangherlini Transformation (TT) is derived from a distinct set of assumptions, most notably absolute simultaneity and rest; however, both the Tangherlini and Einstein–Lorentz formalisms are sub-theories of general relativity and must therefore agree on all coordinate-independent physical predictions. In particular,

they must predict identical point-coincidence locations for the two light signals in Einstein's training scenario. Although the two theories appear to be equivalent in certain respects, it seems highly unlikely that they would converge on the issue of relative simultaneity. Nevertheless, this agreement emerged in a particularly unexpected manner.

As shown in Section 3.3, the point coincidence predicted by the TT is identical to that obtained from the fully covariant LT. Moreover, the mixed-coordinate equations of motion for the light signals—the x' component of the position 4-vector—are exactly the same in both theories, showing that the two equations depend on the velocity v and its direction. This agreement is nontrivial because the two transformations diverge significantly in their fully covariant forms, as expected from their distinct temporal structures.

The striking outcome is that the Tangherlini temporal structure appears to be inherently encoded in the Lorentz transformation. It emerges explicitly and naturally when the LT is written in a mixed-coordinate form, revealing a hidden layer of the structure that is typically obscured by the standard presentation. This observation is remarkable and warrants a general modern STR mathematical treatment beyond the training scenario.

5. Conclusions

This analysis shows that the counterintuitive features commonly attributed to relative simultaneity arise from the synchronisation convention and from interpreting event-point substitution within the direct Lorentz transformation. This procedure produces mixed-representation equations for the time and location of events in the moving frame, which are inherently non-compliant with the reciprocity principle. Therefore, the resulting relative simultaneity reflects a representational artifact, rather than a physical effect.

Using the fully covariance Lorentz transformation (FCLT), we demonstrate that events that are simultaneous in the stationary frame remain simultaneous after the transformation ($\Delta t' = 0$) when the complete transformation is applied to event position 4-vectors. This yields a consistent, frame-independent invariant temporal ordering, satisfies the reciprocity principle, and is fully compatible with the postulates of special relativity.

The ultimate validation of this approach is point-coincidence. As Einstein noted, physical reality consists of material point meetings in spacetime. Our proof shows that the FCLT and the Tangherlini Transformation predict the exact same space-time point-coincidence for intersecting light signals. This intersection point, and not the geometric midpoint of the train, is a physical truth.

We contend that the counter-propagating light signals do not reach the midpoint of the train simultaneously, which is in agreement with Einstein's original analysis. However, this follows directly from the kinematics of the train and signal motion: the midpoint moves towards one signal and away from the other; therefore, a simultaneous arrival at this point is generally not expected. Therefore, the unique invariant point coincidence location, where the signals meet simultaneously, is located elsewhere along the train's longitudinal axis. This behaviour follows directly from the relative motion along the worldlines and does not represent a physically measurable effect of relative simultaneity but rather the effect of the conventional choice of synchronisation. The Tangherlini framework provides an alternative physically valid representation of the same scenario and predicts the same point-coincidence location.

Both the standard Lorentz and Tangherlini transformations can coexist consistently because there is a one-to-one correspondence between their coordinates. More importantly, the invariant temporal ordering of events is already encoded in the structure of the Lorentz transformation when expressed in a

mixed-coordinate form that is identical to that of the Tangherlini transformation. The invariant time ordering appears explicitly in the Tangherlini fully covariant representation, which is often associated with the concept of absolute time. As presented in section 3.4, The mixed-coordinate substitution leads to the inevitable conclusion that a theoretical preferred inertial frame exists because only one frame yields a symmetric point-coincidence location for the two counter-propagating light signals relative to their emission points. The presence of time ordering in both frameworks indicates a deeper structural dependency that warrants further investigation and rigorous modern mathematical generalisation, in particular the possibility of detection whether an inertial frame is the preferred one.

At first glance, our findings may appear unconventional; however, they enrich the special theory of relativity without contradicting its established principles. Long-standing objections concerning the physical status of relative simultaneity are resolved within this framework, as the effect is understood to arise from the synchronisation convention rather than from a physical phenomenon. Rather than revisiting long-standing interpretive positions, these results broaden the conceptual landscape of the study. By clarifying the non-physical status of relative simultaneity and the role of synchronisation conventions, the analysis removes the constraints that have shaped discussions of time since the early formulations of relativity. This may enable genuinely new lines of inquiry in the philosophy of time, grounded in fully consistent relativistic structures.

Acronyms and Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript.

ARF	Absolute Reference Frame
DLT	Direct Lorentz Transformation
EOM	Equation of Motion
FCLT	Fully Covariant Lorentz Transformation
GR	General Relativity
ILT	Inverse Lorentz Transformation
LT	Lorentz Transformation
RS	Relative Simultaneity
STR	Special Theory of Relativity
TT	Tangherlini Transformation

Mathematical Symbols

Symbol	Description
A	Embankment point A
B	Embankment point B
c	The invariant speed of light in a vacuum
c_+, c_-	Apparent variable one-way velocities of light appearing in the intermediate mixed-coordinate representation
(ct, x, y, z)	Spacetime coordinates of an event or location in the stationary frame
(ct', x', y', z')	Spacetime coordinates of an event or location in the moving frame
E	Coordinate system representing the stationary embankment frame.

L_A, L_B	4-vector equations of motion for light signals emitted from points A and B in the embankment frame E
L'_A, L'_B	Mixed-coordinate 4-vector equations of motion for light signals in the moving frame T
$L_{A'}, L_{B'}$	Fully covariant 4-vector equations of motion for light signals in the moving frame T, parameterised by t'
T	The coordinate system represents the moving train frame.
t'_i	The invariant time coordinate of the light signals' point-coincidence in the moving frame T
t_M	The time at which the two light signals intersect in the stationary frame E
v	Constant relative velocity of the train frame with respect to the embankment frame along the x axis
x'_i	The invariant spatial coordinate of the light signals' point-coincidence in the moving frame T
x_M	The spatial coordinate of the intersection of the light signals in the stationary frame E
X_A, X_B	4-vector coordinates of stationary point-events A and B in the embankment frame E
X'_A, X'_B	Mixed representation 4-vector coordinates of point-events A and B in the moving frame T, parameterised by t
$X'_{A'}, X'_{B'}$	Fully covariant 4-vector coordinates of point-events A and B in the moving frame T, parameterised by t'
γ_v	Lorentz factor
Λ_v	Standard Lorentz Transformation (LT) matrix in the standard configuration
Ω_v^∞	Tangherlini Lorentz Transformation (TT) matrix in the standard configuration.

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